

Developmental Focus: A Strategic Educational Framework for Guiding Students Through Critical Transitional Phases, Providing Mediation and Support to Overcome Developmental Challenges

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Abstract. The article discusses the operationalization of a number of ideas on the structure and dynamics of an event. The event itself is presented as a conjugation of transitions from the current state to another, different from what is and functions stereotypically, and, at the same time, from reality as an obvious given to an idea in which the meaning and cultural significance of reality are revealed. This dual transition presupposes overcoming the functional fixity of previous experience, habitual modes of action. A trial action is assumed as a method of overcoming. For an educational event as an act of cultural transmission, this is a trial of a new cultural form, an attempt to reproduce it in one's own action.

Key words: educational event, cultural form, transition, explanatory reading, experience, hope, functional fixation, overcoming, mediation

Today's pedagogical science and practice contain many different-scale innovations, and so quickly changing each other that there is not enough time and means to assess their effectiveness. One of the innovative ideas is the organization and implementation of educational events (EE). An educational event is usually understood as an event that concentrates the creative efforts of teachers and students and provides a breakthrough effect in understanding subject, interdisciplinary and meta-subject content. The methods of designing and conducting, as well as the achievements of such events are described so vaguely that it is impossible to be sure how educational they really are, i.e., how they correspond to the main mission of education - to ensure cultural transmission.

Since any descriptions and references to OS declare its developmental character, when considering OS, we were guided by the ideas about the act of cultural development that are significant for us. According to these ideas, an event is a situation in which a student's encounter with a scientific or aesthetic idea that defines the basis of some field of science or art has come true. The result of such an encounter is understanding and active involvement.

Almost every modern subject in higher education is distinguished by the content disunity of sections and topics. External, of course, since for a specialist all these topics are, of course, connected at least by the unity of the subject and method; but for a student (and often for a teacher) the subject is broken down into discrete, isolated parts, "living on their own". Traditionally, each subject (for example, "General Psychology") is studied as an independent unit, not connected in any way with other fragments of psychological knowledge, "esoteric", without any obvious and effective applied need. It is assumed that it is of special value and is capable of independently

ensuring the development of thinking of a future specialist, however, the lack of correlation with the entire structure of psychological knowledge and the hidden inclusion of the subject in professional activity, the loss of the internal (for students) basis of "need" for them "here and now" are obvious, since nothing specific is required of them in terms of a long-term, life result. The educational tasks, for the sake of mastering the means of solving which, in fact, each course is conducted, are simplified and emasculated to such an extent that they do not bear any imprint of the real tasks (problems) of the given subject. As a result, they are solved by students using the latest of the "formulas" that they received from the teacher in a ready-made form in the last (penultimate) lesson.

Just as the famous literary character happily learned that he had been speaking prose all his life, so education will be pleasantly surprised by the fact that throughout its history, in one way or another, in its best examples and attributes, it has quite successfully sought to develop (build) the activity of modeling with the hands and heads of its students. True, it almost never specifically reflected on this circumstance, considering it a logical stage in improving teaching methods. Now, for the successful reform of psychological education, the task is to cultivate this valuable achievement, providing it with the necessary means and organizing an experimental test under psychological support.

In our understanding, the idea of modeling brings (can bring) decisive heuristics to psychological education (in practical terms, the article is about training psychologists at Surgut State University) in the following way. At first implicit, but as it is included in the modeling activity, acquiring more and more definite outlines (including with the expansion of the range of objects of various nature involved, with the acquisition of experience in solving contrasting problems, etc.), the subject of analysis of future psychologists becomes the "problematic pair": the subject and method of research. Reflection on the subject and method, as well as the means of solving current problems (for example, the obviously coinciding in time beginning and educational correspondence of "General Psychology" and "General Psychology Workshop") constitutes the necessary background for problematization for the development of this course. The tasks and the "super-task" (coursework) set for solution must simultaneously meet the educational and cognitive needs of students. The supertask must be large enough (calculated for a long-term solution - for one or two semesters), since for qualitative transitions "in knowledge" a certain spatial (meaning a significant expansion of the studied conceptual area in comparison with traditional training) and temporal (associated with the development of new forms of research activities, group work, etc.) run-up is necessary.

A new form of conducting classes, which we called a project-based one, must also meet this task. With this form of educational interaction, the goal of joint activity with the teacher and classmates becomes the final product - a solved problem. The personal decentration necessary for the professionalization of a psychologist - overcoming the egocentrism of a philistine position, going beyond the limitations of "countertransference" usually inherent in beginning psychologists, etc. - is a consequence of the psychological atmosphere, which is cultivated mainly by the conditions of cooperation and freedom of choice of the trajectory of educational and professional movement - attributes so atypical for the modern educational situation. At the same time, the means of such decentralization are psychological knowledge itself (this, apparently, is the decisive

advantage of psychology as an academic subject over other disciplines), consistently derived from the research (theoretical and experimental) activities of students.

Problematization of the entire field of psychological knowledge is a necessary condition for the formation of psychological thinking of future specialists. There are no once and for all established truths either in theory or in the practice of a psychologist. Any manifestation of professionalism, from our point of view, is realized primarily in the research nature of psychological work, be it an examination, correction or issuance of specific recommendations. Problematization cannot be delayed in the process of training and dissemination, and not in its result.

The creation of anthologies on various branches of psychology significantly lags behind the development of psychological education, moreover, the anthologies mainly include fragments of purely theoretical views of the authors, and their research, experimental "kitchen" remains beyond the capabilities and attention of the compilers. Because of this, it seems to us, many interesting studies, theoretical constructs and facts are gradually disappearing from psychological use, which significantly impoverishes the learning process and makes practically unattainable that broad erudition that is inherent in all without exception psychological "masters" of the past.

In the course of study offered to students, they, apparently, for the first time have to face a peculiar understanding of science, the tasks of psychology, its history and today's practice. Usually, school and university subjects present "settled" and time-tested truths, if one can say so - the yesterday of science, its tried and tested and generally accepted foundations. The community of psychologists is in a different situation. The crisis in defining the subject and method of our science is, perhaps, already the main and stable background of our daily work - in a scientific laboratory or at an enterprise, in a psychological consultation or at school. The theory and practice of psychology are still not far from introspection, stimulus-reactivity and speculativeness in research and transformation of reality, therefore yesterday continues for us today. At the same time, just as every person witnesses the birth, rise and fall of "absolute" truths throughout his life, and along with worldly wisdom comes to him a sense of the relativity of our knowledge of the world, so the professional movement in any of the human activities, including psychology, inevitably faces the need to revise the relevant fundamentals.

Scientific knowledge does not age, it changes, like everything else on this earth. Scientific priorities, social tasks, research tools change, and this process is continuous. A beginner enters a new profession as if into a running stream, and in order not to remain on the shore and first acquire the speed of the stream, and then surpass it, he should be oriented not only in the known truths, but also in the current circumstances and problems of scientific knowledge, as well as in the future, still poorly understood, still only at the tip of the pen - new tasks and new means of solving them.

In our course of problems we try to move away from traditional didacticism and reveal (emphasize) the relativity of psychological knowledge, give a taste of contradictions and understand the tendencies of movements of theoretical and practical programs. For psychology, perhaps, as for other disciplines of human studies and humanitarian knowledge, there is no past. The ideas of Antiquity and the Renaissance are as relevant and modern today as a computer experiment. Revealing them as "new", we realize that such a presentation has its "pluses" and "minuses". Fresh scientific data are less well structured, they have not yet filtered out externally interfering, but in fact significantly clarifying the picture, subjective and objective circumstances.

However, a widely disclosed palette of psychological worldview gives incomparably more specific and natural images of the ideas dominating in the scientific community, research rules and stereotypes, directions of scientific and pseudo-scientific polemics. This generally reflects the emerging and dominant practice of psychological research, when the scheme of the experiment, since the time of the criticized and rejected introspection, gravitates toward the positivist model of reducing the conditions and content of the psychological world of man, toward the superposition of dependent and independent variables. At the same time, already on the material of biology (physiology), such a mechanistic understanding of the process and technique of studying the organism is unproductive and does not accommodate the evolutionarily variable and orienting-researching essence of the latter.

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